

MODULAR LEARNING FATIGUE AMONG STUDENTS IN CIABU NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the Modular Learning Fatigue among students in Ciabu National High School, Baybay City, Leyte. It aimed to find out the Socio-demographic profiles of the respondents as sex, age, grade level, monthly family income, signs of modular learning fatigue, and level of modular learning fatigue experienced by the students. The respondents of the study were 211 Junior and Senior high school students enrolled in AY 2021 – 2022. The target number of respondents was 30 % of each sex and grade level's total population. Stratified sampling was used and split the population of interest into homogeneous subgroups or strata before choosing the research sample. The study used the descriptive method with a questionnaire as a tool for data gathering. Using the survey as a technique, data on socio-demographic profiles, modular learning fatigue signs, the relationship among socio-demographic profiles, and the level of modular learning fatigue were collected. Descriptive analysis such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and Chi-Square test for the relationship on objective four (4) was used. The findings of the study indicated signs of modular learning fatigue in the respondents' mental, physical, social, and emotional aspects. In the relationship between the Level of modular learning fatigue and Socio-Demographic Profile, the result was significant between monthly family income and the mental aspect of the modular learning fatigue. The relationship was highly significant between the social aspect of modular learning fatigue and the monthly family income. The monthly family income was a big factor in the modular fatigue experiences of the students taking into account that the profile on the students' family income was categorized as poor. For the rest of the socio-demographic profile, the age, sex, and grade level the relationship between these demographic profiles and the level of modular learning fatigue were not significant.

Keywords: *Modular learning fatigue, levels of modular learning fatigue, mental, physical, social, emotional*

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INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the Basic Education – Learning Continuity Plan the roadmap/framework using a participatory approach to guide the Department on how to deliver education in the time of the Covid-19 pandemic while ensuring the health, safety, and welfare of all learners, teachers, and personnel of DepEd.

The Department of Education under the leadership of Secretary Leonor Briones and DepEd officials deliberate on some course of actions or strategies to address learning continuity in both private and DepEd schools. The utilization of media such as radio and television are currently practiced to make education accessible to all learners even among the learners residing in remote areas. Limitations in the use of these techniques are recognized since not all families have the television, radio, smart cellphones where pupils and students can readily avail of themselves. Some developing countries deliver classes through radio, television, and online platforms. The poorest families and students do not have radio, television, and other devices to access the resources and to learn at their homes. So, some developing countries provide resources such as textbooks, radios, equipment, and study guides to the poorest students (Mustafa, 2020).

Many students, too, still need the internet to do supplemental research on more complex assignments. In line with the internet connectivity, DepEd survey shows that of the 6.5 million students who have access to the internet, approximately 20 percent use computer shops or other public places to go online. Worse, 2.8 million students have no way of going online at all. This is especially common in the rural areas where 53 percent of the population live and where both internet access and speed can be a challenge ("In the Philippines, distance learning reveals the digital divide | Heinrich Böll Stiftung Hong Kong | Asia Global Dialogue", 2022). Due to lack of internet connectivity, information technology, educational materials, and digital technology skill distance learning is difficult for teachers, students, and families in developing countries (Mustafa, 2020)

Recognizing technology as a problem, the use of self-learning modules (SLMs) makes learning more feasible and viable. This permits learners to engage in self-learning in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever applies to the learner. The use of modules encourages independent study. One of the benefits of using modules for instruction is the acquisition of better self-study or learning skills among students. Students engage themselves in learning the concepts presented in the module. They develop a sense of responsibility in accomplishing the tasks provided in the module. With little or no assistance from others, the learners progress on their own. They are learning how to learn; they are empowered (Nardo, M.T.B, 2017).

In support to students' self-learning, the Department of Education (DepEd) provides Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) with the alternative learning delivery modalities to be offered for various types of learners across the Philippines.

Despite all the benefits of the SLMs, students still face a lot of challenges in the course of their program. The study of Dangle & Sumaoang (2020) showed that the main challenges that emerged were lack of school funding in the production and delivery of modules, students struggle with self-studying, and parents' lack of knowledge to academically guide their child/children. Hence, it is evident that there are struggles associated with the use of modular distance learning among the students while doing self-learning modules, (FlipScience, 2020)

The challenges encountered by the learners, give rise to a condition known as fatigue which occurs after performing a demanding cognitive task for a prolonged time (Slimani et al, 2018). In modular learning, every high school student has a minimum of nine subjects and every module comprises fifteen to thirty-five pages with a minimum of four activities for each topic and two assessments. It could be seen that most of the learners have difficulty in this new learning modality. 90% of the participants had a hard time answering their modules. Half of them do not have enough time to accomplish all their modules within a week (Dangle & Sumaoang, 2020).

In conformity to Castroverde & Acala, 2021, each student has a total of nine modules to be fulfilled in a single week, because of these, students are vulnerable to fatigue. New research has shed some light on the reason behind this feeling and shows that overloading students causes not only academic stress, but also takes a toll on students' mental and physical health, which, unsurprisingly, hinders learning (Don't overload students: assigning too much work discourages learning 2018)

Performing a cognitively demanding task, exerting a significant amount of efforts such as in vigilance tasks or working memory tasks, for a prolonged time increase the feeling of fatigue. As it increases, individuals will be less willing to stay engaged with the task, i.e., less motivated to continue performing the task. Consequently, a lower level of motivation impairs performance Müller & Apps (2019).

With the aforesaid realities, the need arises to investigate the modular learning fatigue among students in Ciabu National High School. The outcome of the study will be beneficial to school administrators, designated school guidance counselors, and teachers, to recognize students' mental, physical, social, and emotional reactions to fatigue, and strive to better help students manage and cope with the symptoms of fatigue as they continue to engage in modular learning. The findings of the study will pave the way for proposing a school intervention plan to reduce the severity of modular fatigue. Moreover, this research will be beneficial as a reference for policymakers in the field of education to further enhance the implementation of modular distance learning whenever the same situation will happen in the future.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the modular learning fatigue among students in Ciabu National High School. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the students in Ciabu National High School in terms of Age, Sex, Grade Level, and Monthly Family Income?
2. What are the signs of modular learning fatigue experienced by the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 Mental
 - 2.2 Physical
 - 2.3 Social
 - 2.4 Emotional
3. What is the level of modular learning fatigue as experienced by the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1 Mental

- 3.2 Physical
- 3.3 Social
- 3.4 Emotional
- 4. Is there a relationship between socio-demographic profile and the level of modular learning fatigue?
- 5. What can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Ciabu National High School. It is a public High School located at Brgy Ciabu, Baybay City, Leyte. It is considered the biggest High School in the whole district 10 in terms of land area and population. Also, it is established in Baybay City in the year 2007

The respondents of the study were Junior and Senior high school students who are currently enrolled in AY 2021 – 2022. The target number of respondents is 30 % of each grade level's total population. Ciabu National High School has a total population based on the Learners Information System (LIS) School Year 2021–2022 is 710 Learners that is why the target number of respondents was 30% of each grade level total population because if the sample size is too small, it will not yield valid results. An appropriate sample size is required for validity, for populations under 1,000, a minimum ratio of 30 percent (300 individuals) is advisable to ensure the representativeness of the sample (Sample Size – Institutional Effectiveness and Assessment, 2022).

The researcher used stratified sampling and split the population of interest into homogeneous subgroups or strata before choosing the research sample. Grade Levels were evenly distributed for proportional sampling, for grade level seven there were 27 respondents out of the 92 population, grade level eight was 36 respondents out of 120 the population, grade level nine was 44 respondents out of the 145 population, and grade level ten was 36 respondents out of the 123 population, grade level 11 was 39 respondents out of the 133 population, and the grade level 11 was 29 respondents out of the 97 population.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents

GRADE LEVEL	POPULATION	SAMPLE
7	92	27
8	120	36
9	145	44
10	123	36
11	133	39
12	97	29
TOTAL	710	211

Instrumentation

To amass the needed data, the researcher adopted and dispensed structured questionnaires. The questionnaire was divided into three parts.

The researcher sought permission from the proponent of the adopted copyrighted instruments, an electronic email was sent to Helen J. Michielsen of the Fatigue Assessment Scale, Email address: h.j.michielsen@kub.nl. A copy of a letter was labeled as Appendix C. an electronic email was also sent to Lauren B. Krupp of the Fatigue Assessment Inventory, Email address: lauren.krupp@nyulangone.org. A copy of a letter was labeled Appendix D.

Obtaining a copy of the Fatigue Assessment Inventory can be found in the original article published by the developers. Direct Correspondence to: Lauren B. Krupp, Department of Neurology, Stony Brook, NY 11794 – 8121, USA.

The adopted instruments were modified to suit the intended goal of the research which was to know the existing signs of modular learning fatigue and to rate the level of modular learning fatigue experienced by the students in the following areas: mental, physical, social, and emotional.

Part I of the questionnaire identified the demographic profile of students, it included the age, sex, grade level, and monthly family income of the respondents. For the age, they can write the number of years, for the sex they can write male or female, and for the grade level they can write 7 for grade 7, 8 for grade 8, 9 for grade 9, 10 for grade 10, 11 for grade 11 and 12 for grade 12. For the Monthly Family Income, respondents shaded the circle that corresponds to their answer. The monthly family income was based on the latest data from The Philippine Institute for Development Studies. (Poverty, the Middle Class, and Income Distribution amid COVID-19, 2020)

Part II of the questionnaire employed a ten checklist or indicators of the mental, physical, social, and emotional fatigue signs of the respondents while working on the modules. On the mental signs' items, seven, nine, and ten of the Fatigue Assessment Scale were adopted and item nine of the Fatigue Assessment Inventory was adopted. On the physical signs of fatigue items two, three, four, five, and nine were adopted from the Fatigue Assessment Scale, Items two, three, four, and six were adopted from Fatigue Severity Scale, and Items five, six, 18, 19, 21, 22, and 29 were adopted from the Fatigue Assessment Inventory. On the social signs, items 7 and 9 were adopted from the Fatigue Severity Scale, and items one, ten, 13, and 26 were adopted from the Fatigue Assessment Inventory. On the emotional signs, items two, three, and 17 were adopted from the Fatigue Assessment Scale and item one was adopted from the Fatigue Severity Scale.

Part III assessed the level of modular learning fatigue experienced by the students in the following areas: mental, physical, social, and emotional using the scale indicated as follows: (1) not noticeable, (2), mild (3), Strong (4). Very Strong. Respondents check-marked the appropriate column on the indicator/s that described their level of modular learning fatigue.

Data Collection

After the permission was granted from the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Graduate School with the appropriate coordination with the DepEd Baybay City Division Schools Division Superintendent, Ciabu National High School School Head, and Learners' Parents/Guardians, data was gathered by way of a questionnaire. Administration of questionnaires were done per schedule and retrieval of SLMs to facilitate data gathering and retrieval. The data gathered was tallied, categorized, and subject to descriptive and inferential statistical analyses.

Data Analysis

Part I of the questionnaire looked into the demographic profile of the respondents, in terms of age, sex, grade level, and monthly income. It was analyzed using the arithmetic mean for age and frequency counts and percentages for sex, year level, and monthly family income. The socio-demographic profile of the respondents was described using the frequency counts and percentage.

Part II is a checklist that described the signs of fatigue experiences of the respondents based on the given categories: mental, physical, social, and emotional. Frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze this part. Part II instruments were tallied based on how many respondents indicated a checkmark on particular signs of modular learning. It was categorized as mental, physical, social, and emotional and sequence based on the frequency, from most checked signs to the least checked signs of modular learning fatigue.

Part III of the questionnaire described the level of modular learning fatigue as experienced by the respondents according to the scales which ranged from 4 to 1. To measure the level of fatigue, a weighted mean was computed and students' responses were categorized into 4 (Very Strong), 3 (Strong), 2 (Mild), and 1 (Not noticeable). The formula for weighted mean is indicated below:

To describe the modular learning fatigue, the computed weighted mean was categorized as follows:

Table 2. Signs of Fatigue Experiences

WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION	DESCRIPTIONS
3.25 – 4.00	Very Strong	The indicators on Modular Learning Fatigue were very intensely experienced
2.50 – 3.24	Strong	The indicators on Modular Learning Fatigue were intensely experienced
1.75 – 2.49	Mild	The indicators on Modular Learning Fatigue were slightly experienced
1.00 – 1.74	Not Noticeable	The indicators on Modular Learning Fatigue were not experienced

The findings of the study were presented in the form of tables and graphs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the survey on Modular Learning Fatigue Among Students in National High School. This section provides answers to the research questions of the study, which include the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, grade level, and monthly family income. Moreover, all necessary data are in tabular form and are further supported by the appropriate statistical interpretations.

Socio-demographic Profile of the Students

Table 3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents which comprises the age, sex, grade level, and monthly family income. Demographics are statistical data that researchers use to study groups of humans. A demographic refers to distinct characteristics of a population. Researchers use demographic analysis to analyze whole societies or just groups of people. Some examples of demographics are age, sex, education, nationality, ethnicity, or religion, to name a few (What are Demographic Examples, 2022)

Age is a significant variable in the study. In the table presented, the 211 respondents, aged 13 years old and below got the highest percentage equivalent to 45 respondents or 21%. The result is attributed to the fact that the respondents from grade seven and grade eight are mostly 13 years old and below. Age 13 years old and below has the highest number of respondents of 45, because there were ages 13 years and below who belonged to grade-level seven and eight and age 16 years old has the second-highest respondents because most 16 years students were grade nine students who have the highest populations by grade level based on the school year 2021 – 2022 Learners Information System (LIS).

Table 3. Distribution of the Socio-demographic Profile of the Students

Attributes	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in Years)		
13 and below	45	21%
14	33	16%
15	32	15%
16	38	18%
17	29	14%
18 and above	34	16%
TOTAL	211	100%
Average Age (In Years)	Mean = 15.43 Years	
Sex		
Male	84	40%
Female	127	60%
TOTAL	211	100%
Grade Level		
Grade 7	27	13%
Grade 8	36	17%
Grade 9	44	21%
Grade 10	36	17%
Grade 11	39	18%
Grade 12	29	14%
TOTAL	211	100%
Monthly Family Income		
Poor: Below P10,957	158	75%
Low-income but not poor: P10,957 to P21,914	30	14%
Lower middle: P21,914 to P43,828	12	6%
Middle: P43,828 to P76,669	4	2%
Upper middle: P76,669 to P131,484	3	1%
Upper middle but not rich: P131,483 to P219,140	4	2%
Rich: P219,140 and above	0	0%
TOTAL	211	100%

Sex refers to male or female. The result revealed that most of the respondents were female comprising 60% of the total number of respondents which means that females are more engaged in studies like this, however, due to the fact, females have 330 population based on the latest Learners Information System (LIS) and females have high population than males in Brgy Ciabu based on the latest Barangay Management Information System (BMIS) Population.

Grade Level. This is another variable included in the socio-demographic profile. As revealed in the table, grade nine got the highest number of students equivalent to 21%, this is due to the fact that based on the school year 2021 – 2022 Learners Information System (LIS) grade nine has the highest population of 145 learners followed by grade 11 at 18%, grades eight and ten got 17%, grade twelve at 14%, and the least was grade seven with 13%. Grade nine-level during School Year 2021-2022 has the highest population based on the School year 2021 – 2022 Learners Information System (LIS) population record. Aside from the population records, the result of high respondents on the higher-grade level particularly in grade-level nine

may be attributed to the fact that in the K to 12 curriculum, as you progress to a higher-grade level the higher the competencies to cover. The K to 12 Program covers Kindergarten and 12 years of basic education (six years of primary education, four years of Junior High School, and two years of Senior High School (SHS]) to provide sufficient time for mastery of concepts and skills, develop lifelong learners, and prepare graduates for tertiary education, middle-level skills development, employment, and entrepreneurship (What is k to 12 program? 2022)

Monthly Family Income was also measured and it revealed that 75% of the respondents were Poor or it has a family income below 10,957 Pesos monthly. The 10,975 Peso Monthly Income is categorized as poor based on the latest data by The Philippine Institute for Development Studies. This means that most of the students belong to this category, which may attribute to modular learning fatigue. Poor students tend to experience modular learning fatigue since they have difficulty complying with subjects that would require various materials such as Android/Smart Phone, Internet Connectivity Kit, and basic writing tools. The result agrees with (Dollanganger, 2022) who cites that most public-school students who come from less privileged families, their mental health has become a major concern during this period of transition due to Covid -19 Pandemic. Noteworthy, in the Philippines, financial struggles have started to worsen for poor families during the outbreak due to an unprecedented economic shutdown (Ade, 2020). Consequently, a poor learning environment is detrimental for students to comfortably participate in remote learning. This difficulty has been repetitively revealed in students' responses. Establishing a positive and conducive learning space has long been a problem in distance education, especially in most poor households (Baticulon et al., 2020).

Signs of Modular Learning Fatigue

The modular learning signs of fatigue are categorized into mental, physical, social, and emotional aspects. Table 3 presents Mental Signs of Modular Learning Fatigue.

To assess the respondents' mental signs of modular learning fatigue there are ten indicators that the respondents checked if they experienced such. The result is presented in Table 3.1

The indicator on "Confuse on what module to answer first was ranked 1. It goes to show that Confusion was the most experienced sign of modular learning fatigue among learners in modular learning education. This implies that when students received their module in all their subjects, they get to experience difficulty in organizing which subject to attend to and in effect they experienced mental fatigue.

Table 3.1 Mental Signs of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	No. of Responses	%	Rank
Confuse on what module to answer first	140	14%	1
Encounters difficulty in maintaining focus and concentration.	121	12%	2
Environment distractions affect modular learning.	113	11%	3.5
Difficulty in organizing ideas	110	11%	3.5
Mind goes blank while answering the activities and assessment	98	10%	5.5
Experiences absent-mindedness.	95	10%	5.5
Difficulty in answering the module lowers my esteem and confidence.	92	9%	7
Awful thoughts linger while doing the modules that I can't answer	79	8%	8.5
Prone to forgetting important things.	79	8%	8.5
Thoughts of inadequacy and incompetence creep in which affect my performance.	56	6%	10
Total	983	100%	

Furthermore, the DepEd Basic Education learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) requires Modular Distance Learning that involves individualized instruction that allows learners to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format whichever is applicable in the context of the learner. The teacher takes the responsibility of monitoring the progress of the learners (DepEd, 2020), which means that learners' education will continue with the unfamiliar mode of education. This difficulty in remote learning has been confirmed in the study of Sundarasan et al., (2020) where university students in Malaysia expressed stress about the overwhelming number of assignments required by the teachers. Their findings also revealed that this difficulty had a huge impact on the stress and anxiety levels of the students. The same experience was also reported by Sarvestani et al., (2019) where students complain about the extensive volume and the large number of modules that they need to answer.

To assess the respondents' physical signs of modular learning fatigue there are ten indicators that the respondents checked if they experienced such. The result is presented in Table 3.2

Table 3.2 Physical Signs of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	No. of Responses	%	Rank
Encounters headache and body pains.	110	15%	1
Unable to rest and sleep at night	96	13%	2.5
Experiences drowsiness that blocks me from answering the modules	94	13%	2.5
Lacks the energy to engage in my usual physical exercise.	83	11%	4
Loses appetite in eating regular meals.	72	10%	6
Goes through difficulty in getting up for my daily activities	71	10%	6
Feels lethargic and not able to do my module	70	10%	6
Experiences muscle and body tension	55	8%	8
Unable to do personal hygiene.	42	6%	9
Come across breathing difficulty and heart palpitation.	33	5%	10
Total	983	100%	

Table 3.2 indicated the signs of modular learning fatigue in the physical aspects of the learners of modular learning education. It revealed that the indicator Encounters headache and body pains was Ranked 1 which could imply that the modular learning had heightened their fatigue which resulted in headaches and body pains during and after working on their modules and that headaches and fatigue could be interconnected. Fatigue and lack of energy is also frequent complaint of people who suffer from migraine headaches. Headache could be a sign of a migraine disorder, sleep disorder, dehydration, or several other chronic illnesses. Fatigue is a common symptom of many conditions including depression, sleep disorders, and fibromyalgia (Healthline, 2022). These reactions were mentioned by Sundarassen et al.,2020 that another concern of students is their compromised physical health. Students spend almost the entire day for online classes and answering activities, thus giving them less time or no time to engage in physical activities. This issue has been similarly raised by students in Malaysia where they experience strains of attending 6 to 8 hours of online classes, which further worsen their stress level. In addition, a wide variety of behaviours, including increased phone usage, decreased physical activity, and fewer locations visited, are associated with fluctuations in Covid-19 news reporting (Huckins et al. 2020).

To assess the respondents’ social signs of modular learning fatigue there are ten indicators that the respondents checked if they experienced such. The result is presented in Table 3.3

Table 3.3 Social Signs of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	No. of Responses	%	Rank
Prefers to stay home all the time rather than going out.	114	16%	1
Feels out of place whenever I am in a group of people.	95	13%	2
Shy away from my friends and peer group	88	12%	3.5
Prefers to be alone rather than to be with other people.	86	12%	3.5
Runs out of energy to engage in pleasurable activities such as leisure time and other hobbies	73	10%	5.5
Declines the invitation from friends, relatives, and peers during special occasions.	71	10%	5.5
Hesitates to open up my concerns to significant people.	67	9%	7
Avoids bonding with family members.	51	7%	8
Sudden loss of interest in engaging in social media.	37	5%	9.5
Delist friends in my social media accounts.	35	5%	9.5
Total	717	100%	

The signs of modular learning fatigue on social aspects of the learners on modular learning education were Ranked 1 in the indicator Prefers to stay home all the time rather than going out and Ranked 2 in the indicator Feels out of place whenever I am in a group of people. It goes to show that Connecting with other people is the most experienced sign of modular learning fatigue among learners in modular learning education. This could mean that respondents tend to experience isolation while doing their modules. Staying at home has resulted in having poor interaction with other people whenever they get the chance to go out. This result conforms to the research of Sundarassen et al., 2020 that building rapport and maintaining relationships is crucial for positive mental well-being. Unfortunately, the COVID19 pandemic has resulted in a “social recession” (Sundarassen et al., 2020), which created prolonged social distancing patterns.

To assess the respondents' Emotional signs of modular learning fatigue there are ten indicators that the respondents checked if they experienced such. The result is presented in Table 3.4

Table 3.4 Emotional Signs of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	No. of Responses	%	Rank
Experiences helplessness when there is no one to turn to in answering difficult activities and assignments.	126	14%	1
Faces so much pressure in beating up school deadlines.	110	12%	3
Feels guilty with little mistakes.	105	12%	3
Feels very insecure over unanswered modules.	103	12%	3
Observes changes in one's mood.	88	10%	5.5
Get slighted and irritated even in small matters.	85	10%	5.5
Gets impatient with people: family members, and peers.	74	8%	8
Encounters anxiety in doing school tasks.	72	8%	8
Experiences feelings of breaking out.	72	8%	8
Undergoes nervousness when holding modules in different subjects.	56	6%	10
Total	891	100%	

Based on table 3.4, the manifested Signs of modular learning fatigue on emotional aspects of the learners were indicators of Experiences helplessness when there is no one to turn to in answering difficult activities and assignments; Faces so much pressure in beating up school deadlines, Feels guilty with little mistakes and Feels very insecure over unanswered modules Experienced helplessness was Ranked 1 while the rest of the indicators were Ranked 3. It goes to show that Pressure and insecurities were the most experienced sign of modular learning fatigue among learners in modular learning education. When students have difficulty in answering their modules and there is no one else that they could run to, they tend to have poor perspective in terms of their abilities to do school tasks and when this happens it will have a negative effect on their self-concept. Creating poor image about themselves will add to their insecurities. These implications are supported by the study of Kerres, 2020 that gaining teacher support is essential for students' learning, boost their self -image thus lower their insecurities.

The Level of Modular Learning Fatigue

This study also looked into the level of modular fatigue of the respondents in the aspects of mental, physical, social, and emotional aspects of the learners.

To assess the respondents' Level of Modular Learning Fatigue in the mental dimension, there are ten indicators by which the respondents rate their experience. The result is presented in Table 4.1

The three highest indicators in the mental aspects were as follows: I have trouble staying focused and concentrated with a weighted mean of 2.37; I have difficulty organizing my ideas in answering the activities in the module with a weighted mean of 2.35, and Thoughts of inadequacy and incompetence creep in which affect my performance with a weighted mean of 2.34. Poor concentration is the inability to focus on a task. Although mild, those with the

highest mean a person who is unable to concentrate is easily distracted. Performance at work or school could be affected if one could not concentrate.

Table 4.1 Mental Level of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level of Modular Fatigue
I have trouble staying focused and concentrated.	2.37	Mild
I have difficulty organizing my ideas in answering the activities in the module.	2.35	Mild
Thoughts of inadequacy and incompetence creep in which affect my performance.	2.34	Mild
Distractions from the environment affect my modular learning	2.29	Mild
Every time I cannot answer a module, I get the impression that I am the dumbest person in the class	2.24	Mild
When I'm doing my modules, I think of awful things like I don't have the capacity to answer	2.21	Mild
I tend to overlook important matters.	2.21	Mild
I experience confusion on what module to answer.	2.16	Mild
I get mentally blank as I progress in answering the modules.	2.12	Mild
Various preoccupation hinders me from answering my modules.	2.11	Mild
Total	2.24	Mild

A person who could not think well affects his/her decision-making (What Makes You Unable to Concentrate? 2022). For these top three indicators, the level of modular fatigue is mild which means that the fatigue experienced was slight or minor and that they still have control over the situation and are aware that something can still be done.

To assess the respondents' Level of Modular Learning Fatigue in the physical dimension, there are ten indicators by which the respondents rate their experience. The result is presented in Table 4.2

Table 4.2 Physical Level of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level of Modular Fatigue
I feel sleepy while answering the module.	2.41	Mild
I feel weary and just too tired to work on my modules	2.28	Mild
I have difficulty getting up early for my morning routine.	2.11	Mild
I cannot anymore do my physical exercise just the way I do it before.	2.09	Mild
I feel sick and experience headache, body pains while answering the activities.	2.05	Mild
I have difficulty getting up early for my daily activities.	2.03	Mild
I have difficulty resting and sleeping.	1.99	Mild
It is hard for me to calm down and relax.	1.96	Mild
I lack the appetite in eating my meals.	1.91	Mild
I experience heart palpitation and breathing difficulty.	1.64	Not Noticeable
Total	2.05	Mild

As reflected in table 4.2, The total weighted mean is 2.05 the interpretation is mild or the experience of the indicator was slight or minor and the top 3 indicators were as follows: I feel sleepy while answering the module with a weighted mean of 2.41; I feel weary and just too tired to work on my modules with a weighted mean of 2.28; I have difficulty getting up early for my morning routine with a weighted mean of 2.11. The level of modular fatigue of these three indicators was mild and described as slight or minor. Respondents' reactions when asked to work on their modules have negative effects on them. The result connotes that when a person starts to think negatively, it will affect their body. The body reacts to the brain signals that make individuals feel lethargic and weak. This implication is supported by Earl E. Bakken Center for Spirituality & Healing, that negative attitudes and feelings of helplessness and hopelessness can create chronic stress, which upsets the body's hormone balance, depletes the brain chemicals required for happiness, and damages the immune system (Taking Charge of Your Health & Wellbeing, 2022)

On the other hand, the indicator I experience heart palpitation and breathing difficulty obtained a mean of 1.64 and the level of modular learning fatigue was not noticeable or described as unobserved. This could mean that the respondents were not able to experience this indicator and the modular learning fatigue did not affect the cardiovascular according to Richard Nelesen, PhD; et al fatigue has a measurable relationship with cardiac functioning. There were no significant fatigue effects on simple measures such as HR or BP (The Relationship Between Fatigue and Cardiac Functioning, 2022)

To assess the respondents' Level of Modular Learning Fatigue in the social dimension, there are ten indicators by which the respondents rate their experience. The result is presented in Table 4.3

Table 4.3 Social Level of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Level of Modular Fatigue
I prefer to stay home rather going out.	2.37	Mild
I prefer to stay alone rather than being with other people	2.27	Mild
I have hesitations in sharing my problems with significant people.	2.12	Mild
I shy away from my friends and classmates who reach out to me.	2.08	Mild
I do not have the energy to engage in healthy pleasurable activities like spending time for leisure and talent.	2.05	Mild
I feel out of place when I am in a group of people.	1.98	Mild
I decline the invitation from my friends and relatives during special occasions.	1.92	Mild
I lost my interest in engaging in social media.	1.81	Mild
I avoid bonding with family members.	1.74	Not Noticeable
I unfriend significant people on my Facebook	1.71	Not Noticeable
Total	2.01	Mild

Furthermore, the level of modular learning fatigue did not only affect the respondents physically but also socially. As can be seen in table 4.3 the top 3 indicators were as follows:

I prefer to stay home rather going out with a mean of 2.37; I prefer to stay alone rather than be with other people with a mean of 2.27, and I have hesitations in sharing my problems with significant people with a mean of 2.12. The level of modular learning fatigue of these three indicators was mild and described as slight or minor. The result implies that modular learning fatigue, a lot of times, could make an individual socially inhibited because building rapport and maintaining relationships is crucial for positive mental well-being. However, since the description is only mild, this connotes that the respondents were still able to maintain a sense of balance. Amidst the busy schedule, they still had time to go out and interact with their environment. This implication is supported by Michelle M. Kazmer's journal on Coping in a Distance Environment that students in a distance learning environment often find themselves in new educational surroundings supported by unfamiliar technologies. As they adjust to this learning environment, they may rely on available people and tools for support, as well as changing their own living and learning patterns (View of Coping in a distance environment: Sitcoms, chocolate cake and dinner with a friend, 2022).

It is also notable in the result that there were indicators in the social aspect which obtained a mean of 1.74 for the indicator I am avoiding bonding with family members and a mean of 1.71 for the indicator "I unfriend significant people on my Facebook". These two indicators have a Not noticeable or the experience of the indicator was unobserved of modular learning fatigue. The result shows that in terms of social aspect the respondents' have gained external support from their families so this could explain why the result is unnoticeable. Most of the time respondents turn to their families if they experience problems. In addition, respondents also tend to divert their attention on social media hence, the level of fatigue in the social aspect is least likely to occur by blocking significant people on Facebook. The result can be explained in the study of Sundarasan et al., 2020 that the COVID19 pandemic has resulted in a "social recession", which created prolonged social distancing patterns, thus, making emotional support probably impossible at this state.

To assess the respondents' Level of Modular Learning Fatigue in the emotional dimension, there are ten indicators by which the respondents rate their experience. The result is presented in Table 4.4

Table 4.4 Emotional Level of Modular Learning Fatigue

Indicators	Weighted Mean Level of Modular Fatigue	
I feel so helpless when I cannot find people who can help me out in answering difficult activities in the module.	2.40	Mild
I feel so pressured and in a hurry all the time	2.32	Mild
I feel insecure over unanswered modules.	2.22	Mild
I easily get impatient with family members and other people.	2.18	Mild
I experience extreme mood swings	2.12	Mild
I easily get slighted and irritated even in small matters.	2.12	Mild
I get anxious about doing other school tasks.	2.07	Mild
I cannot laugh at my own mistakes	2.06	Mild
I feel nervous when I start doing my modules.	2.00	Mild
I feel like I am going to break out.	1.96	Mild
Total	2.15	Mild

Aside from the level of modular fatigue in the social aspect, respondents also feel affected emotionally. As reflected in table 4.4, the top three indicators were as follows: I feel so helpless when I cannot find people who can help me out in answering difficult activities in the module with a mean of 2.40; I feel so pressured and in a hurry all the time with a mean of 2.32; and I feel insecure over unanswered modules with a mean of 2.22. The level of modular learning fatigue of these three indicators was mild and described as slight or minor. The description of mild or slight implies that although they feel helpless, pressured, and insecure, they were able to do something about it in order not to get overwhelmed which often leads to other serious mental health conditions. This implication is supported by Sundarasan et al., (2020) where university students in Malaysia expressed stress about the overwhelming number of assignments required by the teachers. Their findings also revealed that this difficulty had a huge impact on the stress and anxiety levels of the students. The same experience was also reported by Sarvestani et al., (2019) where students complain about the extensive volume and the large number of modules that they need to answer.

Significant Relationship Between Level of Modular Learning Fatigue and Sociodemographic Profile

This section determined if there is a significant relationship between the Level of modular learning fatigue in the mental, physical, social, emotional, and Socio-Demographic Profiles of the respondents in terms of age, sex, grade level, and family income.

As reflected in Table 5, the relationships among the variables were tested using Chi-Square at a 0.05 Alpha level of significance by applying the P-Value Test.

Table 5. Relationship Between Level of Modular Learning Fatigue and Sociodemographic Profile

Modular Learning Fatigue	Socio-Demographic Profile	Chi-Square Value	Df	p-value	Contingency Coefficient	Significance
Level of Modular Learning Fatigue (Mental)	Age	7.534 ^a	10	.674	.194	Not Significant
	Sex	2.227 ^{ns}	3	.527	.102	Not Significant
	Grade Level	7.516 ^{ns}	10	.676	.194	Not Significant
	Monthly Family Income	11.624 [*]	4	.020	.229	Significant
Level of Modular Learning Fatigue (Physical)	Age	14.211 ^{ns}	15	.510	.251	Not Significant
	Sex	5.858 ^{ns}	3	.119	.164	Not Significant
	Grade Level	22.922 ^{ns}	15	.086	.313	Not Significant
	Monthly Family Income	3.889 ^{ns}	6	.692	.135	Not Significant
Level of Modular Learning Fatigue (Social)	Age	9.773 ^{ns}	10	.461	.223	Not Significant
	Sex	2.855 ^{ns}	3	.415	.116	Not Significant
	Grade Level	10.930 ^{ns}	10	.363	.235	Not Significant
	Monthly Family Income	16.728 ^{**}	4	.002	.271	Highly Significant
Level of Modular Learning Fatigue (Emotional)	Age	9.574 ^{ns}	10	.479	.220	Not Significant
	Sex	.352 ^{ns}	3	.950	.041	Not Significant
	Grade Level	7.516 ^{ns}	10	.676	.194	Not Significant
	Monthly Family Income	0.532 ^{ns}	9	.997	.050	Not Significant

The Mental Level of Modular Learning Fatigue, Age Sex, Grade Level, and Monthly Family Income

The computed value of Pearson Chi-Square between the level of modular learning in mental aspect and age is 0.674. The null hypothesis (Ho) chi-square test means the result indicated no significant relationship between the level of modular learning fatigue in the mental aspect and age. This claim is further supported by our p-value test at the 0.05 significance level which yielded a result of a computed p-value that is less than the significance level ($p\text{-value} < \alpha$; $0.674 < 0.05$). This could mean that the age of the respondents did not affect the level of modular learning in terms of the mental aspect. According to Kendal Corporation, Endurance can decline as you age — and you can tire more quickly — but fatigue is not a natural part of aging (Aging and Fatigue: 4 Common Causes, 2022)

The computed value of Pearson Chi-Square between the level of modular learning in mental aspect and sex is 0.527. The null hypothesis (Ho) chi-square test means the result indicated no significant relationship between the level of modular learning fatigue in mental aspects and sex. This claim is further supported by our p-value test at the 0.05 significance level which yielded a result of a computed p-value that is less than the significance level ($p\text{-value} < \alpha$; $0.527 < 0.05$). This could mean that the level of modular learning fatigue had nothing to do with sex. According to JSTOR Organization, these gender-specific biological factors do not sufficiently explain the reported sex differences in fatigue (Gender Differences in Fatigue, 2022)

The computed value of Pearson Chi-Square between the level of modular learning in mental aspect and grade level is 0.676. The null hypothesis (Ho) chi-square test means the result indicated no significant relationship between the level of modular learning fatigue in the

mental aspect and grade level. This claim is further supported by our p-value test at the 0.05 significance level which yielded a result of a computed p-value that is less than the significance level ($p\text{-value} < \alpha$; $0.676 < 0.05$). This could also mean the level of modular learning fatigue has nothing to do with the grade level. According to the study by Pelders and Nelson, Fatigue was attributed to various factors, including the working hours, work conditions, and workload. The potential influences of demographic and socioeconomic factors, living conditions, commuting times, lifestyle, and health or wellness were also discussed (Pelders, J. and Nelson, G., 2019)

The computed value of Pearson Chi-Square between the level of modular learning in the mental aspect and monthly family income is 0.020. The null hypothesis (H_0) chi-square test means the result indicated a significant relationship between the level of modular learning fatigue in the mental aspect and monthly family income. This claim is further supported by our p-value test at the 0.05 significance level which yielded a result of a computed p-value that is less than the significance level ($p\text{-value} < \alpha$; $0.020 < 0.05$). The result could mean that the level of modular learning fatigue in the mental aspect has been affected because of the family income. As reflected in table 2 for the family income, most of the respondents were categorized as poor. Poor families have a share of financial difficulties due to the high cost of commodities. Concerning modular learning, the financial constraint will hinder study productivity and the utmost concentration of students are at stake (Chang & Fang, 2020). According to Baticulon et al., 2020 Consequently, a poor learning environment is detrimental for students to comfortably participate in remote learning. This difficulty has been repetitively revealed in students' responses. Establishing a positive and conducive learning space has long been a problem in distance education, especially in most poor households. Furthermore, students have a wide range of distractions when studying at home. For example, not all are able to find suitable spaces for home learning, or studying may be constrained by insufficient hardware and unstable networks (Zhang et al. 2020).

The Physical Level of Modular Learning Fatigue Age, Sex, Grade Level, and Monthly Family Income

The computed value of Pearson Chi-Square between the level of modular learning in physical aspect and age was 0.510. For modular learning fatigue in physical aspect and sex, the computed value of Pearson Chi-square was 0.119 while for grade level the computed p-value is 0.086 and between the level of modular learning in the physical aspect and monthly family income, the computed p-value was 0.0692. The result indicated no significant relationship between the level of modular learning fatigue in physical aspects and age, sex, grade level, and monthly family income. This means that respondents' age, sex, grade level, and monthly family income have nothing to do with the level of modular learning fatigue in the physical aspect. According to the study by Pelders and Nelson, 2019 fatigue was attributed to various factors, including the working hours, work conditions, and workload. Furthermore, Pelders and Nelson mention that potential influences of demographic and socioeconomic factors, include, living conditions, commuting times, lifestyle, and health or wellness.

The Social Level of Modular Learning Fatigue Age, Sex, Grade Level, and Monthly Family Income

Moreover, the computed value of Pearson Chi-Square between the level of modular learning in social aspect and age is 0.461. For modular learning fatigue in social aspect and sex, the computed value of Pearson Chi-square is 0.415 while for grade level the computed p-

value is 0.363 and between the level of modular learning in the social aspect and monthly family income, the computed p-value is 0.002. The result indicated no significant relationship between the level of modular learning fatigue in social aspects and age, sex, and grade level. This means that the variables on age, sex, and grade level have nothing to do with the level of modular learning fatigue in the social aspect. However, the result showed high significance between the level of modular learning in the social aspect and monthly family income. This claim is further supported by our p-value test at the 0.05 significance level which yielded a result of a computed p-value that is less than the significance level ($p\text{-value} < \alpha$; $0.002 < 0.05$). This could mean that respondents' level of modular learning in the social aspect was affected by the monthly family income. This further implies that the lower the family income is, there is a tendency for students to experience social isolation. A poor learning environment is detrimental for students to comfortably participate in remote learning. This difficulty has been repetitively revealed in students' responses. Establishing a positive and conducive learning space has long been a problem in distance education, especially in most poor households (Baticulon et al., 2020). According to the article of Hendrix, 2019 research has found that learning environments play a crucial role in student success. Several factors can affect learning ability, including seating, light, noise, and even colour. Students who study in a positive learning environment have been shown to be more motivated, engaged, and have a higher overall learning ability. On the other hand, students learning in poor environments – those that are uncomfortable, loud, or full of distractions – will find it far more difficult to absorb information and stay engaged.

The Emotional Level of Modular Learning Fatigue and Age, Sex, Grade level, and Monthly family Income

The result also showed that the computed value of Pearson Chi-Square between the level of modular learning in emotional aspect and age is 0.479. For modular learning fatigue in emotional aspect and sex, the computed value of Pearson Chi-square is 0.950 while for grade level the computed p-value is 0.676 and between the level of modular learning in the emotional aspect and monthly family income, the computed p-value is 0.997. The result indicated no significant relationship between the level of modular learning fatigue in emotional aspects and age, sex, grade level, and monthly family income. According to Better Health Channel Fatigue can be caused by a number of factors working in combination, such as medical conditions, unhealthy lifestyle choices, workplace problems and stress (Fatigue, 2022)

In line with the findings of the study, an action plan is designed to address the modular learning fatigue of the learners in Ciabu National High School. A detailed presentation of the proposed intervention plan is found in the Appendix section.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings the following conclusions were drawn.

Seventy-five percent of the respondents belong to poor or below 10,957 pesos monthly family income which means the supposition was most of the learners are vulnerable to fatigue due to their family financial nature that inept them to adapt to the changes brought by the Covid-19 pandemic. Indicated signs of modular learning fatigue in the respondents' mental, physical, social, and emotional aspects concluded that the frequency of modular learning fatigue signs affects the level of modular learning among the respondents. Levels of modular learning fatigue were mild which means although respondents have modular learning fatigue, they were able to adapt and manage to have a mild level of modular learning fatigue.

In the relationship between the Level of modular learning fatigue and Socio-Demographic Profile, the result was significant between monthly family income and the mental aspect of the modular learning fatigue, the inference on this was that the monthly family income of the respondents greatly affects the mental levels of the respondents because coping up need resources and the lack of resources can aggravate fatigue hence the relationship was significant. The relationship was highly significant between the social aspect of modular learning fatigue and the monthly family income, the implication was monthly family income affects the socialization of the respondents because part of socialization involves income, and lack of this results in isolation among respondents hence the relationship between the social level of modular learning fatigue and monthly family income was highly significant.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are presented based on the findings and conclusions of the study:

1. Coordinate with parents to check on the wellness/health of the learners and emphasize the importance of their involvement in the health and learning of their children.
2. Suggest a break in between classes to avoid the significant effect of modular learning fatigue among learners.
3. Proposed for the implementation of School Intervention Plan to eliminate mild modular learning fatigue among the learners in Ciabu National High School.

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